

science and policy
for a healthy future

Form:
Pro-Forma Invoice

Valid since: **October 2017**

Version: **V 1.0**

8.3 ANNEX 3

Pro-Forma Invoice

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Page 1 of 1

Sent by/Shipper		Sent to/Receiver		
TAX ID/VAT no.		TAX ID/VAT no		
Contact name		Contact name		
Company name		Company name		
Street Address		Street Address		
City, Zip Code		City, Zip Code		
Country		Country		
Phone		Phone		
Fax		Fax		
Email		Email		
Invoice Number				
Reason for Export				
ID	Detailed Description of Goods	Quantity	Country of Origin	Value and Currency
Responsible Person		Name		
		Telephone number		
		Email		
I declare that the above information is true and correct to the best of my knowledge.				
Date:		Name:		Signature:
Company Stamp				

